

USELESS COLLEGIA

I. Nominally Useless Collegia + The Red Thread

The reconciliation of irrational forms in which certain economic relations appear and assert themselves in practice does not concern the active agents of these relations in their everyday life. And since they are accustomed to move about in such relations, they find nothing strange therein. A complete contradiction offers not the least mystery to them. They feel as much at home as a fish in water among manifestations which are separated from their internal connections and absurd when isolated by themselves.¹

– Karl Marx

The socio-cultural and socio-political “cut” of nearly three decades of scholarship focused primarily on Renaissance Italy and patronage – i.e., from the early 1960s to the late 1980s, and said to have started with Gombrich and then more or less petered out due to exhaustion – is utterly misleading regarding what was actually at stake in Renaissance Italy in terms of the multiple arts at the close of the Late Medieval period.² It is also a sign of the times in which it was written, crossing as it does the post-war cultural revolution and the onslaught of neoliberalism. If Marx may be detected in some of these examples of misprision (intentionally biased sociological misreadings), it is primarily due to the fact that he made his own shallow dive into Renaissance Italy to extract both a critique of the art of his own time (i.e., the pietist art of Wilhelmine Germany and Hegel’s complicity with that regime) and some gestures toward the supposed origins of capitalism and the commodification of life via “merchant capital” and urbanization.³ Patronage and capital then share a common terrain, reaching back into antiquity, and, oddly enough, that terrain intersects with incremental urbanization – the expansion of towns and cities where the merchant classes tended to congregate.⁴ Here we are not far from Baxandall’s “dancing merchant savants” as the true sponsors or progenitors of the Italian Renaissance, although with blaming urbanization and/or blaming the merchant classes we are further from the real point (the Hegelian “real of the real”) than ever. Reducing art to socio-cultural ashes to perform a forensic report on origins may resemble science, but it obliterates all traces of what was actually present, prior to incineration, as trace or impress of “origin”; i.e., how the ontic conceals the de-ontic. Renaissance patronage was, according to the scholars of this thirty-year war of words irredeemably linked to urban dynasties – both aristocratic and capitalist-mercantilist.⁵ The obsession with Florence, mostly by Anglo-American scholars, and known as “florentinitis” (a term coined by a Milanese scholar to ridicule the shallow and somewhat pretentious glorification of the Florentine Renaissance) is also utterly disfigured by the obvious recourse to the Medici, the balance of Florentine history generally consigned to flames (along with all dissenting factions deposed or corrupted by the despotism of the Medici).

Thus Venice ... and the Venetian Renaissance. No less self-righteous than Medici Florence, the Venetian Republic was, at the least, truly heterodox. Patronage in Venice may have followed similar trends (determined by the materialist histories scholars of the period love to cite and then mostly ignore), but it was of an entirely different

¹ Karl Marx, “Chapter XLVII: Genesis of Capitalist Ground-rent,” pp. 763-93, in *Capital: A Critique of Political Economy, Vol. 3*, ed. F. Engels (Moscow: Foreign Languages Publishing House, 1962), p. 760. And: “What Hegel says with reference to certain mathematical formulas applies here: that which seems irrational to ordinary common sense is rational, and that which seems rational to it is itself irrational.” Ibid., with reference to the irrationality of “the relation of a portion of the surplus-value, of money-rent [...] to the land [as such],” viz., there is no logical relation whatsoever. Ibid., p. 759.

² See F.W. Kent, Patricia Simons, J.C. Eade (eds.), *Patronage, Art, and Society in Renaissance Italy* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002). First published by Australian National University (ANU) in 1987 and based on the May 1983 conference at ANU, “Patronage, Art and Society.”

³ For the appearance and disappearance of Marx across the terms of engagement for this extensive foray into Renaissance Italy, see Margaret Rose, “Marx and the Study of Patronage in the Renaissance,” pp. 313-319, in *ibid.*

⁴ It is the carriage trade that Marx implicates in his analysis, and the buying cheap and selling dear practices associated with it. “Merchants capital, when it holds a position of dominance, stands everywhere for a system of robbery, so that its development among the trading nations of old and modern times is always directly connected with plundering, piracy, kidnapping slaves, and colonial conquest; as in Carthage, Rome, and later among the Venetians, Portuguese, Dutch, etc.” *Capital: A Critique of Political Economy, Vol. 3*, pp. 325-26. See p. 328n50 regarding the English in India and a “string of futile and really absurd (in practice infamous) economic experiments”; e.g., the creation in Bengal of “a caricature of large-scale English landed estates.” Marx compares the trading nations to intermediate worlds similar in spirit to the *intermundia* of Epicurus (and Lucretius) where the gods live. Ibid., p. 325.

⁵ In *Capital, Vol. 3*, Marx makes several telling remarks (in part via excoriating citation in footnotes) regarding the battles between the nobility and the merchant classes, the latter robbing the people, and the former robbing the latter.

order. What was this other order? Various justifications exist for calling it a “mythic order” – but in contradistinction to the cooked histories that potentates commissioned in the Renaissance to offer up a “classical” edge to their dynasties (in the manner of Suetonius and Livy, again according to scholars of the thirty-year war of words noted). The mythic and the classical therefore diverge. In terms of art and patronage the difference is significant. By the time of the Renaissance, and inimically so, the writing of history (historiography proper) was intentionally *literary*. It was an artform. And perhaps it is fair to say that multiple disciplines followed suit – including the multiple visual arts. In Venice, for example, the literary and the artistic realms were totally mixed up with one another in a type of dance that at times resembled a danse macabre. The sudden appearance of the printing press had quite a bit to do with this commingling of interests, as did Venice as international entrepot. If artistic-literary license was “born” in this period, it is also a misnomer for something far more interesting.⁶ In a sense it might be better to say it was a matter of artistic-literary *dissent* than *license*, both terms nonetheless retrospectively applied to events that are, indeed, markers for what we like to call the emergence of modernity. The echo a few hundred years later in the French Enlightenment only serves to underscore that the so-called modern did emerge through dissent, and that patronage was linked and complicit in all that preceded that emergence and all that followed.⁷ Links to the artistic exception in both eras tend to confirm this. Dismissing the exception remains, as a result, incredibly difficult and/or incredibly self-serving, by scholars and by patrons. Both Kant and Hegel defended “uselessness” as the principal sign of the work of art. If it had overt utility, it was generally demoted to craft.

The body is also a horse. Sometimes the horse becomes a nightmare. Is *this* not culturally determined? Yet what is the vehicle of the work of art? Is it not what has come to be called the exception – i.e., the “soul” of the work, as Diderot and others would eventually spell out in opposition to the forms of patronage present in the *ancien régime*? The body of the work of art is the ontic level; and this level is privileged through the mechanisms of patronage. If you wish to dissent, you will have to produce intentionally un-authorized works and present *them* as such. How? And where? You can “write” them with impunity, but can you also edition them with impunity in a real or virtual police state? The “soul” of the work is the true vehicle – the de-ontic level (arguably also its agency). How it “travels” through worlds, dodging the “merchant class” operating on behalf of the police state of capital, becomes the answer to all questions. Where it leads others is an open question: primarily because it almost always depends on others.

“Walk away from illness ...” “Pick up thy bed and walk ...” “Habit is a great deadner ...”

Habit as “great deadner” ... A quip by Beckett, with a sting. Perhaps habit here is Bourdieu’s *habitus*? Walking away from *habitus* ... How? Leaving the Fountain of Bethesda and carrying your bed ... Where to? Present-day patronage and its various contagions are not so much different than in Kierkegaard’s “present age.”⁸ The same life-less patterns remain. The still-born works produced under prevailing conventions only prop up the illnesses of the age – variable and viral, symptomatic and full-blown. The necessity of the exception remains, and its enemies are all more or less those who have decided to placate power and privilege, plus those unhappy souls wishing for access to

⁶ Amidst the claims of scholars of the Italian Renaissance we find statements such as: “In fact, it was only in the course of the Renaissance that art created *consciously as such* emerged as a specific kind of object; and much of the ‘art’ that fills our museums today never achieved that distinctive status at the time.” Richard Goldthwaite, “The Empire of Things: Consumer Demand in Renaissance Italy,” pp. 153-75, in *ibid.*, p. 153; italics added. Goldthwaite is troubling and agreeing with Bourdieu’s claim that art cannot inhabit “a sacred island systematically and ostentatiously opposed to the profane, everyday world of production, a sanctuary for gratuitous disinterested activity in a universe given over to money and self-interest.” *Ibid.*, with reference to Pierre Bourdieu, *Outline of a Theory of Practice*, trans. Richard Nice (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press: 1977), p. 197; first published *Esquisse d’une théorie de la pratique: Précédé de trois études d’ethnologie Kabyle* (Genève [Paris]: Droz, 1972). The birth of artistic license supposedly occurred in opposition to the “learned advisors” who ran the systems of patronage – i.e., the middlemen. See F.W. Kent, Patricia Simons, “Renaissance Patronage: An Introduction,” pp. 1-21, in *Patronage, Art, and Society*, p. 17; with reference to Charles Hope, “Artists, Patrons, and Advisors in the Italian Renaissance,” in Guy Fitch Lytle, Stephen Orgel (eds.), *Patronage in the Renaissance* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton, 1981), pp. 293-343, and H.W. Janson, “The Birth of ‘Artistic License’: The Dissatisfied Patron in the Early Renaissance,” in *ibid.*, pp. 344-53.

⁷ If the chief characteristic of the Italian Renaissance was that it was pagan, the chief characteristic of the French Enlightenment is that it was secular. Scholars also love to argue over the actual date of the emergence of modernity, with the primary moments being either the Italian Renaissance or the French Enlightenment.

⁸ Søren Kierkegaard, *The Present Age: On the Death of Rebellion*, trans. Alexander Dru, The Resistance Library (New York: Harper Perennial, 2019). First published as a pamphlet in 1846. This translation first published by Oxford University Press under the title *The Present Age and Two Ethico-Religious Treatises* in 1940.

power and privilege. False consciousness, indeed. Enslavement by choice; illness by indoctrination. False consciousness comes often from unconsciousness. Illness is of body and soul; the former the register where symptoms first appear, the latter where the antidote or exit may be prepared. Psychology, sociology, art history are paths into and out of the dark wood. Purgatory and Limbo. As stations en route elsewhere, both are, indeed, socially constructed chimera – hallucinatory and spectral. The *habitus* is an old cloak. Better to walk naked ...

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Kierkegaard draws out the consequences through a series of feints that nonetheless contain an aberrational foray into truth-telling insofar as his goal is to define into oblivion the alienated soul of the artist (and self-identity is at play here as much as any objective analysis he may have derived from his own struggles with Hegel):

The law governing artistic production applies, on a smaller scale, to every one in daily life. Every man who has a real experience experiences at the same time all its possibilities in an ideal sense, including the opposite possibility. Aesthetically these possibilities are his lawful property. Not so, however, his private and personal reality. His talk and his production both rest upon his silence. The ideal perfection of his talk and of his production will correspond to his silence, and the absolute expression of that silence will be that the ideal will include the qualitatively opposite possibility. But as soon as the artist prostitutes his own reality he is no longer essentially productive. His beginning is his end, and his very first word will be a sin against the modesty of the ideal. This type of artistic production is therefore even, aesthetically speaking, a kind of private gossip. It is easily recognized because it is not balanced by its opposite; for ideality is the balance of opposites. For example, if the man who is moved to write by suffering is really initiated into the realm of ideals, he will reproduce the happiness as well as the suffering of his experience with the same affection. The condition of his attaining this ideal is the silence with which he shuts off his own personality. Otherwise, in spite of all precautions, such as changing the scene to Africa, his one-sided predilection will be privately recognizable. For an author, like any one else, must have his own private personality, but it must be his own *åbåtv* [Holy of Holies]; and just as the entrance to a house is barred by the crossed bayonets of the guards, the approach to a man's personality is barred by the dialectical cross of qualitative opposites in an ideal equilibrium.⁹

And:

Only by suffering can the “unrecognizable” dare to help on the levelling process and, by the same suffering action, judge the instruments. He dare not overcome the levelling process directly, that would be his end, for it would be the same as acting with authority. But he will overcome it in suffering, and in that way express once more the law of his existence, which is not to dominate, to guide, to lead, but to serve in suffering and help indirectly. Those who have not made the leap will look upon his unrecognizable action, his suffering as failure; those who have made the leap will suspect that it was victory, but they can have no certainty, for they could only be made certain by him, and if he gave that certainty to a single person it would be the end of him, because he would have been unfaithful to the divinity in desiring to play at being an authority: that would mean that he had failed; not only by being unfaithful to God in trying to use authority, but because he did not obey God and teach men to love one another by compelling himself, so that even though they begged him to do so he should not have deceived them by exerting authority.¹⁰

In the context of the complex topology of his acerbic and often doubly ironic critique of culture in 1846 (i.e., by troubling his own authorial voice), Kierkegaard says “all of this,” in his prevailing tone of self-deprecating high seriousness and then deigns/feigns to “disown” it: “But I break off. All this is only fooling, for if it is true that every man must work for his own salvation, then all the prophecies about the future of the world are only valuable and allowable as a recreation, or a joke, like playing bowls or cards.”¹¹ Kierkegaard's categories are not mutually exclusive; they only appear so in the contingent terms engaged. That is the beauty of his topological project. It is up to the reader to “disarm” the ironies (doubled and otherwise) – they are, after all, forms of revelation. His wise exposition resides in that topological excess – not dissimilar to other artists and authors who have indulged the same.

To further escape this self-established trap, Kierkegaard splits himself in two, as do most artists when faced with a potential stalemate in works and through works, but foremost while embroiled in the agency of the life-work:

⁹ Kierkegaard, *The Present Age*, pp. 44-45. This “silence” appears to be an aspect of works-based agency, and the warning concerning prostituting one's inner reality an aspect of honoring works-based agency ...

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 59. Here we have a veiled reference to a necessary modesty, with self-interest as the enemy of the truth(s) of/for works. It is also, *almost*, a “biblical” injunction ... Authorial presence is negated – or so it seems.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

If the genius is an artist, then he accomplishes his work of art, but neither he nor his work of art has a *telos* outside him. Or he is an author, who abolishes every teleological relation to his environment and humorously defines himself as a poet. Lyrical art has certainly no *telos* outside it: and whether a man writes a short lyric or folios, it makes no difference to the quality of the nature of his work. The lyrical author is only concerned with his production, enjoys the pleasure of producing, often perhaps only after pain and effort; but he has nothing to do with others, he does not write *in order that*: in order to enlighten men or in order to help them along the right road, in order to bring about something; in short, he does not write *in order that*. The same is true of every genius. No genius has an *in order that*; the Apostle has absolutely and paradoxically, an *in order that*.¹²

Magnificently, with these statements by Kierkegaard we are both inside of and traversing the critical decade of the 1840s, when many such souls, troubled by the stasis instilled by bourgeois capitalism, and the complicity of artists and scholars with bourgeois capitalism, are engaged in both an internal insurrection and an external insurrection. This is the decade when Marx “enscribed” *The German Ideology* (1845-46). It is impossible not to see the young Marx astride the same dilemmas – inclusive of the ongoing rebellion of the Left Hegelians against Hegel, with “mediation” almost always the great dybbuk. Battling Hegelianism had actually become part of the problem of the decade, and escaping its orbit would take substantial firepower.¹³ If the 1840s prepared the way for Schopenhauer and Nietzsche, the historical detritus includes that epic gamesmanship that scholars play across centuries, dismissing one another along the way and being dismissed, in turn, by those who come later. Some, however, escape such censure by never having actually arrived. Kierkegaard is one such soul, his life-work barely acknowledged outside of Denmark and only taken to task inside Denmark, in its day.

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Ernst Bloch only requires eight pages in *On Karl Marx* to dispose of the French Revolution, on behalf of Marx (and on behalf of the Creative Marxism of the 1950s), and by implication the earlier American and English revolutions, which he only refers to obliquely.¹⁴ The dismissal rests upon the fact that, in such cases, the revolution freed the bourgeois subject (*l’homme*) and, in each case, the primary freedom obtained through the Declaration of the Rights of Man was the freedom to *own property*. He nonetheless does see buried in the internal logic of the French Revolution, no matter how mystified, and amidst its claims to a liberal civil society, the promise of a next step, which would then be on behalf of all citizens and lead to the true humanitarian project of Marxism. The *soi-disant* “economic program of the day” was, irreducibly, and again on behalf of Creative Marxism (i.e., in a kind of doubled retrospection), the “egotistic dynamics of individual production”; for, “private property determines the content of freedom.”¹⁵ Bloch refers to this as a “decline in the stature of the citizen [...] insofar as the nation had not yet surrendered the ground in which the flowers of true freedom bloom.”¹⁶ According to Bloch, “Marx and Engels pointed to the complete success of this revolution as the emancipation of the bourgeois, and the profit system then required by the economy – a reference which could not be made without sharp criticism of the ideology of human rights itself.”¹⁷ That said, it was “not quite enough ...”

¹² Søren Kierkegaard, *Of the Difference between a Genius and an Apostle*, in *The Present Age: On the Death of Rebellion*, pp. 86-87. Written in 1847. This splitting in two will be echoed in the parable of the Knight of Infinite Resignation and the Knight of Faith ...

¹³ See Ernst Bloch, “Marx as a Student,” pp. 9-15, in *On Karl Marx*, trans. John Maxwell (London: Verso, 2018). First published as *Über Karl Marx* (Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp Verlag, 1968), from *Das Prinzip Hoffnung: in fünf Teilen*, 2 vols. (Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp Verlag, 1959). *On Karl Marx* first published in English by Herder and Herder, 1971. “The most obviously unique characteristic of the young Marx was his objective and youthful vigor amid the surrounding post-Hegelian decay. The young philosopher was concerned essentially neither with himself nor the insipid flatlands about him; instead he reflected the light of a world that had not yet come to be but on whose horizon he stood.” *Ibid.*, p. 11.

¹⁴ Regarding Creative Marxism, see Gavin Keeney, “Anamnesis,” pp. 7-76. *Dossier Chris Marker: The Suffering Image* (Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2012). Notably, Bloch does not distinguish between Young Marx and Late Marx, as many will do in Post- or Late-Marxism, or that which follows Creative Marxism. The splitting into two is generally for the purpose of getting rid of the Young (Left) Hegelians, once and for all, and of which the Young Marx was, in fact, a partisan – dissenting or otherwise.

¹⁵ Ernst Bloch, “Man and Citizen in Marx,” pp. 46-53, in *On Karl Marx*, p. 47.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

Marx's discovery of "private property as dominant among the other human rights" led to the conclusion that all of the other human rights were thus duly disfigured.¹⁸ The four bourgeois human rights as of 1791 were via "Bloch + Marx": 1/ *propriété*; 2/ *sûreté*; 3/ *résistance*.¹⁹ The abolition of private property thus remained the Holy Grail of true Marxian communitarianism. Thus, in the "*program of socialism*" (the italics belong to Bloch), "the quest for the rights of uncompromising objective criticism, followed by pragmatic intervention" is the primary means to overcome the last obstacles.²⁰ "The result would be that the *citoyen* would be pulled back out of the abstract-moralistic transcendental world which he inhabited in the ideology of the French Revolution, into the mundane world appropriate to socialized humanity."²¹

The image of the *citoyen*, when still in the bourgeois womb, so to speak, suffered an injury which has exercised its effects subsequently, because it was not recognized initially. But the whole image of the *citoyen*, notwithstanding its diverse sources [classical and otherwise], and even its pernicious stewards [Jacobins, Cromwellians, etc.], continued – even as a slogan – to exert an effective critical force against its contrary [the bourgeois subject], as it developed; indeed, it always contained within itself, as Hölderlin showed, renewed self-purification.²²

What is quite beautifully conveyed here by Bloch, in part via the reference to Hölderlin, is that the "still abstract and idealistic, ideal-construct of the *citoyen*" carries with it the hoped-for remedy to the half-baked freedom of the bourgeois subject.²³

Lastly, then:

When Marx denounces private property as the bourgeois barrier to human rights, he does not reject freedom, the resistance of the people to oppression, and security, as other rights. But he concentrated on the forward effect of Right, which no private property can impede or ultimately destroy. Marx criticized private property by the standard of the very radiance and humanity of the human right to freedom. Freedom is the viewpoint from which his conclusions follow: not freedom of property but freedom from property; not freedom of industry but from the egotism of industry; not emancipation of the egotistic individual from merely feudal society but the emancipation of all men from every type of class society.²⁴

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[...]

If we can believe the stories of Lenin in exile, the revolutionary cadre he organized and supported before his fateful return to Russia included some revolutionary brigands – i.e., a small group (including Stalin) that practiced "expropriations" by theft (quite literally, armed robbery). Perhaps thinking of themselves as honorable and red Robinhoods, or inspired High Romantic highwaymen, they are said to have robbed banks, while Lenin milked socialist sympathizers, which in one case included a "millionaire" merchant. Lenin's personal income, derived from family resources, including an estate, and modest proceeds from his writings (clandestine and otherwise) could not, accordingly, have fully supported his various and extensive peregrinations, nor his penchant for somewhat elegant

¹⁸ Ibid., p. 49.

¹⁹ Ibid., p. 47.

²⁰ Ibid., p. 50.

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid., p. 49.

²³ Ibid., p. 47; i.e., *citoyen* as "allegorical moral person," until otherwise realized, *ibid.*, pp. 52-53. The fact that Bloch repeatedly refers to Hölderlin is instructive. He is one of the few German idealists of the pre-Hegelian High Romantic moment (Jena, etc.) that does not take a serious beating across the diatribe of every instance of liberation being externalized and materialized or damned as wishful thinking and transcendentalist obscurantism. Both Marx and Bloch (and Bloch is effectively and/or channeling Marx) take German Idealism to task for its in-borne tendency and other-worldly pretensions. At the same time, however, they quietly extol the value of the inward revolution, the inner revolt, insofar as it eventually becomes acted upon *in the world*. Most contentious of all, however, is *how* it is to be acted upon in the world. For Marx and followers, it is through class warfare. Bloch does not shy away from stating what he (via Marx) considers the just desserts of the aristocracy and the resistant bourgeoisie. It will take a demon such as Lenin to show the consequences of "what is to be done."

²⁴ Ibid., pp. 49-50.

accommodations while traveling abroad. His finances thus included what little he actually earned by his own labor, some family money, and what he and his cadre managed to beg, borrow, or steal.²⁵

Who, then, are the true revolutionary “creditors” – those who actually pay the price for revolution? Are they not the long-suffering – the proletariat that Marxist ideology expected would bring about the much-anticipated revolt? How is such a revolt prepared? It may be argued that revolt is first prepared ideationally, by creative dissent, across systems of classical patronage that are quite often difficult to detect and define but easy to dismiss, and that the materialization of revolt depends on many factors, including chance and/or fate. The generally maligned mystification of the revolutionary ethos proceeds nonetheless via both immaterial and material means. They are hand in glove, so to speak, which sometimes translates into the velvet fist. If ethos is vaporous and essentially a-historical (or literary-historical), telos is material and historical. Hegel therefore prepared the way for Marx by developing both strands simultaneously. In Kierkegaardian terms, Hegel operated as *prophet*, not literary artist or philosopher. If the Marxist-Leninist materialization of revolt thus took a severe historical-materialist turn, it by no means discredits the immateriality that prepared its way and often sustains the agency of the event across serial failures. The issue becomes what, in fact, the Young Hegelians were debating throughout the 1840s – i.e., what forms of mediation (historical, socio-political, artistic, and philosophical) might be privileged to foster a proper cultural renaissance and/or revolution in Wilhelmine Prussia and, by extrapolation, across Europe. Reaction had already set in, against Romanticism and against idealism, while Western anarchism and nihilism were vying with socialism for the attention of the intelligentsia. Russian nihilism, in particular, fomented a literary renaissance across the 1800s. Dostoevsky, Gogol, and Tolstoy may all be said to have embraced Romanticism and idealism through literary-artistic means, with a touch of emergent realism. They were poets as much as novelists. And the nihilist element had more to do with the absence of a proper addressee for this cultural phenomenon other than a fairly broad Russian bourgeoisie dabbling in liberalism. The “nothingness” or zero degree embraced was the proleptic void all such insurgencies inhabit before blossoming. The Symbolists carried the flame up to the first failed full-blown revolt against the State (with Soloviev dying in 1900). The Futurists and the Supremacists carried the flame after the first failed full-blown revolt and up to and through the October Revolution, only to be marginalized and dismissed across the 1920s, in the Soviet Union, and summarily disowned and discredited with the arrival of Stalin and Socialist Realism. The avant-garde moved West, by degrees, and, in art-historical terms, across rolling insurrections associated with modernism. One movement followed another, each one subsumed by the culture industry along the path of the twentieth century. Teleology now underwrote art history, as an insurance underwriter covers the possibility of a fiasco at sea in the carriage trade.

[...]

We see the true revolutionary creditors every day, if we do not practice aristocratic blind sight (walking quickly, eyes slightly downcast, through streets and squares). They are legion because they are that great abstraction known as Everyman. But they especially include the ones whom we find begging for spare change on the main thoroughfares (the corporatized high streets) of our “world-cities” – or wandering amidst the clamor of the tourist

²⁵ This story is told in a book produced in the post-glasnost Yeltsin years, with the author having access to “all the secret Soviet archives.” See Dmitri Volkogonov, *Lenin: A New Biography*, trans. Harold Shukman (New York: The Free Press, 1994). Given the origin and timing of this book, it is clearly aimed at demolishing the last vestiges of the “myth” of Lenin. The book also seeks to blame the travesties of Stalin on Lenin, not to absolve Stalin but to show that Lenin led to Stalin. Wresting control of “social production” from the aristocracy, the church, and the bourgeoisie apparently required brutality from the get go. While tarnishing the legend of Lenin may be the goal, it is also possible that promulgating the legend of Lenin has come full circle. That said, the book has a certain aura of propagandistic American influence that must be taken into account despite the acclamations by jacket blurb from a Harvard professor, a Stanford professor, and a Boston University professor. The Editor’s Preface is quite telling insofar as it establishes a datum from which there is effectively no return for the reader: “Lenin’s malign influence was imbibed by all subsequent Soviet leaders.” Harold Shukman, “Editor’s Preface,” pp. xxiii-xxviii, in *ibid.*, p. xxvii. Shukman and Volkogonov are pining for the liberal, social-democratic February Revolution of 1917 and its compromises. Thus, Lenin is blamed for the repressions of the 1930s (“the inhuman collectivization and the great terror”) even though he was long dead. *Ibid.*, p. xxvii. Curiously, Bloch in a very telling passage regarding Marx’s necessity of overcoming Feuerbach refers to a polarization in love for humanity that requires “an equally concrete pole of hate.” Bloch, “Changing the World: Marx’s *Theses on Feuerbach*,” pp. 54-105, in *On Karl Marx*, p. 89. “Without the partisanship of the revolutionary class standpoint there is only a ‘retrogressive idealism’ and not a praxis that moves ahead. Without the primacy of the human intellect directed to action all the way, there are only mysteries of dissolution instead of a dissolution of mysteries.” *Ibid.* The “all the way” thus includes class warfare.

hordes (caught in the abject splendor of the commercium of official cultural production). Venice, Rome, London, Barcelona, Zagreb, Ljubljana, New York, Mumbai, Hong Kong, Melbourne ... It hardly matters which world-city you visit. Sometimes they are selling trinkets to cover for the fact that they are begging (to avert any "civil" ordinances against begging). Sometimes they are the dispossessed Aborigines (such as in Fitzroy, Melbourne), who take the money you give them and promptly throw it away. We often find the truest of true revolutionary creditors drinking beer in the morning on a park bench, alone or in groups of similarly minded, apparently lost souls. These foremost creditors are also on the commuter buses in world-cities; e.g., the woman in a wheelchair, who lets out a screech when the bus driver almost misses her stop. The revolutionary creditors are not all so similarly indisposed, however. Yet some have paid more dearly than others. They are young and old; rich and poor. They are damaged and they are entirely wholesome. They stroll as much as they stagger. Some saunter. They ride bikes to work and visit the gym. Yet within this class of universal citizens, subjects *are* subjects. It is tautologically sound to say so. It is impossible to argue with a tautology. There is no dialectic. Yet "Subject to what?" becomes the main question. The unbearable presence of myriad homeless souls in world-cities begs the question for the self-proclaimed "guardians of the cultural commons" how such an abomination could come about.²⁶ Blaming the victim never works. Blaming the victor usually does work. Walking away from illness might just mean, at times, walking away from your masters.

"Subject to mediation" becomes the most obvious answer to the question "Subject to what?" – and mediation takes many forms, including ideological form (also known as socio-political subjugation). It can be openly repressive subjugation or very subtle. It hardly matters. Often enough we are mediated into oblivion, regardless of subtlety or brutality. This more than accounts for why both Romanticism and idealism privileged subjective states over and above the social order. The Kantian critique of reason and Fichte's subjective idealism in many senses prepared the way for German idealism – for Hegel. Mediation is quite readily styled as indoctrination or socialization. Socialization is a key Marxist term for what needs to occur to bring the revolutionary ethos down to Earth, from the stars, and into play – or, out of the self-absorbed egotist and into everyday praxis. It is for this reason that "Bloch + Marx" object strenuously to the ideational and ideological impositions of variations on the theme of endlessly deferred gratification, foremost when it is offered as a reward for "waiting" or – worse yet – complicity ... This is the tired and worn-out Marxist metaphor of "opiates for the people," in which art sometimes is included. This includes all of Marx's objections to German Idealism and its hypostases (as Bloch calls anything reified into the nothingness or the pointlessness of wishful thinking). Religion becomes an obvious target, but only the organized catechisms of other-worldly rewards for remaining quietly enslaved. Bizarrely and brazenly, at times – i.e., to those who think Marxism is co-equal to atheism – there is a powerful messianic and theological current running through Marx's life-work. The a-theological tenor is red herring.²⁷ Like Hegel, he functioned as prophet. The messianic element comes through in Bloch's writings on Marx when he waxes poetic about artists and scholars past who have embodied in works the spirit of revolt. Beethoven is an example. Ultimately, it would seem that art is a revolutionary and absolute form of dissent when and if it sheds all forms of instrumentality and mediation to simply speak.²⁸ Art, too, is tautological at its highest octaves. It simply is. The various means to ends disposed of include forms of mediation that destroy the voice of the work and impose an external voice to justify its presence. Useless collegia abound, via systems of patronage or not, dictating terms of engagement, whereas *totally useless collegia* are what is required, via systems of patronage or not. The apparent singularity in such instances includes the manifold

²⁶ There is an utterly devastating moment in Jean-Luc Godard's *Éloge de l'amour* (2001), when interviews are being conducted toward some sort of film and one hapless soul rounded up for a walk-on role is asked, "When are you most afraid or despondent?" – or such. He tells them that he is most afraid or most vulnerable when he is down to his last cigarette, or when his shoelace breaks. Such is the existential datum for a zero degree for "citizens." *Éloge de l'amour (In Praise of Love)* (2001). DVD. Directed by Jean-Luc Godard. New York: New Yorker Video, 2003.

²⁷ It is instructive to note that it was via *a-theology* that theology was permitted back "inside" the Humanities ...

²⁸ In speaking of "Marx + Bloch," it is necessary to emphasize that Bloch is writing well after the age of revolutions has passed. Creative Marxism is in many ways a restoration of many of the literary-artistic elements abandoned in Late Marx and subsequently troubled across the twentieth century by Marxists as they attempted to keep the catechisms of revolt under the rule of "social production." Bloch's "Changing the World: Marx's *Theses on Feuerbach*," in *On Karl Marx*, returns repeatedly to this hyper-materialist formulation ... The catechism of "social production" obliterated all traces of transcendentals and *ahistorical praxis*. While Feuerbach grounded Hegel, according to "Marx + Bloch," Marx's major task in the 1840s was to ground Feuerbach and then move beyond him ... Marx's *The German Ideology* (written in 1845-46) would be the rite of passage for this final break. Marx's *The Holy Family* would be the transitional rite of passage ... The major works of Feuerbach, to which Marx was responding included: *The Essence of Christianity* (1841); *Preliminary Theses toward the Reform of Philosophy* (1842); and *Principles of the Philosophy of the Future* (1843).

... Works produced across works-based agency, as life-works, only appear as “products.” The culture industry excels at defining their status as objects and as properties. Yet they are incessantly indeterminate and productively incommensurate, as such. They are not produced in isolation, and they draw on the inordinate fire-power of prior art. The modernist white cube gallery is an embarrassment of riches. Ownership of such works is a parody of the very concept of property. If, as Proudhon declared, “all property is theft,” it is theft because it originates in a plenitude that is wholly collectively “owned” – not determined. Much of it pre-exists any form of social determination. The universal citizen may be an abstraction, but the origins of the concept are sound. Mediation is relative to the work at hand ...

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[...]

One of the great blind spots in Marx concerns the concept of the given – i.e., that which pre-exists human appropriation and that which represents a type of pure outside extolled by philosophers since time immemorial. He must out of necessity to his agenda negate or sublimate anything given, as it is in his worldview a mystification. This has more to do with his version of classic materialist necessity (Epicureanism, etc.), which he struggles with, than anything modern – i.e., Marx flirts with the default skeptical position of abject materialism that requires that everything be subject to utilitarianism and material transformation through use, even if in his most inspired moments he leaps all bounds and delivers the *coup de grâce* for all forms of rote instrumentalization that are not in the best interests of his own abstracted version of humanity (*humanitas*). It is in such moments that he reveals his Romanticism ... It is mesmerizing in *Capital* to see him claim, for example, that land has no value until it is cultivated.²⁹ In turn, he then savages the very concept of rent. Without saying so, he is actually valorizing the fact that land is purely *given* and that its use-value is relative to all appropriations. Something cannot be appropriated if it is not already a given. The temporality of givens is at play here – they are originally given or they are given, taken, given back, and taken, over and over again across the ages until the prevailing rational faculties of the day have assumed they are all fictitious, factitious, and suspect, all at once. What Marx is actually up to is demolishing *social* givens, but he cannot quite say so – which is correct given his somewhat totalizing agenda. He just cannot escape the orbit of his own neo-classical construction of necessity. This necessity tends to take the form of a rite of passage to Utopia – viz., it must merely be endured. The “true realm of freedom” begins with necessity and leads to the “development of human energy” in/for itself.³⁰ The Hegelian return here is stunning ... Marx’s saving grace is that he will then disown private ownership of property and thus resurrect the concept of the given under other auspices – i.e., that collective ownership is the only form of ownership that is of value (and within that re-construction he steps into moral philosophy, which he has previously dismissed for its alliance with theological versus social concerns).³¹ Red goes black at times, in Marx, as he steps into a type of self-imposed nightmare only to emerge on the other side of an apparent irrationality with the keys to the kingdom which he quietly extols in passages of his early writings that negate vapid materialism – one of many nemeses he slowly destroys en route to a vision of the earthly paradise he pre-ordains through his transposition of the Hegelian dialectic to a Marxian dialectic. He does not so much turn Hegel upside-down or on his head as inside-out. Spirit in Hegel was also communitarian, whereas in Marx it is both communitarian and materialist. Givens return in Paradise, apparently, though they are banished en route to Paradise. Negation tends to be proleptic at times ...

The same is true of subjectivity as of all other givens – there is nothing until there is the social. The zero degree is necessary for Marx to seal off his analytic from anything pre-existing his analytic. Subjects are formed *only* through social praxis. This so closely resembles his negative approach to the “pure outside” (reduced to a mechanistic materialism in the archaic period) due to the fact that Paradise is to be completely fabricated by humanistic orders

²⁹ Marx, *Capital*, Vol. 3, p. 797. This occurs in the section denoted by Engels as “The Trinity Formula,” pp. 794-810 ... Marx is discussing what he calls “vulgar economy.” “*Capital – Profit* (profit of enterprise plus interest), *Land – Ground-Rent*, *Labour – Wages*, this is the trinity formula which comprises all the secrets of the social production process.” Ibid., p. 794. And: “Vulgar economy actually does no more than interpret, systematize and defend in doctrinaire fashion the conceptions of the agents of bourgeois production who are entrapped in bourgeois production relations.” Ibid., p. 797. Marx then delivers his concluding blow: “It should not astonish us, then, that vulgar economy feels particularly at home in the estranged outward appearances of economic relations in which these *prima facie* absurd and perfect contradictions appear and that these relations seem the more self-evident the more their internal relations are concealed from it, although they are understandable to the popular mind.” Ibid.

³⁰ Marx, “The Trinity Formula,” *Capital*, Vol. 3, p. 800.

³¹ His *given* is a taken-back and, then and only then, a given ...

and anything nominally pre-existing in the world or in subjects must be bracketed and/or discredited. There is an inverted Absolute here, for the “here and now” – or, immanence writ large – and a type of conscious void created from which to proceed. Yet this also betrays or discloses the fact that Marx, as Hegel before him, requires rather strenuous *conceptual* tricks to pull the rabbit out of his magician’s hat.³² The rabbit is the free subject in a free world – i.e., humanity proper is duly freed from enforced forms of subjective alienation (including religious alienation as found in Feuerbach or existential alienation as found in Stirner) through communitarian praxis across worlds. The hat is “Marxism” ... Private worlds must be banished to permit the collectivity to emerge. Private property must be banished to permit the emergence of the agency of Paradise. What was purely given must be renounced – although, in Marx, it is claimed that such never actually existed. Once inside the trajectory of the hoped-for Paradise, the tautology instilled is: “Everything is capital – until it is not ...” This occludes any concept of anything preceding that telos of productivity as forward-marching entelechy. It is Aristotelean in the extreme. Platonism is also banished. There is no going backward – no anamnesis.³³ Knowledge in/for itself is banished as well. All mythic reserves (e.g., Socrates via Plato) that may have led to entering this tautological, historical-materialist state are mooted – viz., they are made doubly immaterial and rendered by sundering as either merely retrospective and vaporous conceptualizations or reactionary mystifications. Yet, in a sense, normative time-senses collapse under duress – and in the Marxian analytic the eschaton appears on or over the horizon. Eschatology famously demolishes teleology. It has to be pushed to The End Times such that it does not destroy the trajectory of the work prematurely. The Young (Left Hegelian) Marx seems to imply that through works we may reach a time and place that has always been the promise of our status in the world. What else is a promised land? The eschaton is the Promised Land. Should anyone claim that it inheres in worlds, they would be asked to prove it. The only proof thus far, across all ages, is the work of art. The Promised Land can be prepared as much through the revolutionary work of art as through revolutionary social production. In many ways, and as attested by art history, such works of art re-load what Marx has suppressed – the banished givens of cultural production. Many such works start from the exact zero degree that Marx utilizes for social praxis. The only difference is that they often head off into the purely negative coordinates of the apophatic path Marx abhors, only to return by a transposition or transfiguration (*catasterism*) of effects and affects Marx would never be able to see or accept, in principle or in fact. His brutal take-down of anything resembling negative theology is telltale for what it, in turn, negates. Nihilism, for Marx, is egotism. Yet he is riding the crest of a wave that might be compared to the greatest sleight of hand in all Hegelian mischief (neo-Hegelian and Hegelian mischief) – i.e., the majestic negation of negation, which is only ever possible after near-endless trial and error (historically or personally).

Ernst Bloch will summarize these proverbial “swerves all over the road,” by Marx, as follows: “Precisely because genuine hope within the world proceeds by way of the world and works through the mediation of the world’s objective process, it is engaged in a venture together with this process, and they stand in the *front line* together.”³⁴

Mediation again ... It seems unavoidable. The question must then be, “What form of mediation?” Most forms of modern and modernist collegia are nominally useless, given they are also parasitical in most cases.³⁵ They feign usefulness but are useless. Another way of mediation must be sought, one that is *truly, totally, or utterly* useless versus only apparently useless as ruse for appropriation, indoctrination, usurpation, and alienation.³⁶ They will feign uselessness and, thereby, be – paradoxically – very useful in their uselessness to the re-discovery of the Promised Land both on the far horizon, at the historical demise of Capital, and always already “here and now,” buried in the majestic and unrecognizable a-historical time-senses of works of art, below and within the physical and intellectual rubble of Capital as it implodes.

The true revolutionary creditors for both Marx and Lenin include artist-scholars past, present, and yet to come – including many either ignored, banished, or embraced by Marx and Lenin.

³² This may actually be the “ideal” mark of genius ...

³³ The mythic is the mythic (and, in Marx and others, a negative tautology); it does not exist, as such (to rationality), except as illusory some-thing else. Yet all magicians know that illusion is the point (i.e., the truth of the illusory).

³⁴ Bloch, “Karl Marx and Humanity: The Material of Hope,” pp. 16-45, in *On Karl Marx*, pp. 39-40.

³⁵ Nominal – “adj. 1. existing, etc. in name or word only, not in fact [...] 2. [...] much below actual value given or received.” A.S. Hornsby, E.C. Parnwell, *Oxford English-Reader’s Dictionary*, New Edition (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1979), p. 333.

³⁶ True – “adj. [...] 1. in accordance or agreement with fact [...] 3. genuine; rightly so named. 4. correct. Ibid., p. 553. Total – “adj. complete; entire.” Ibid., p. 545. Utter – “attrib. adj. complete; total.” Ibid., p. 565.

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[...]

II. Totally Useless Collegia + The Red Thread

Any study of cognitive capitalism and how the hearts and minds of citizens are colonized and subverted by Capital in the twenty-first century will have to reach back into the past, to the origins of Capital (arguably in the Early Modern period), yet concerning itself with the present-day, post-contemporary condition and focusing upon forms of artistic scholarship, where possibilities exist for absolute dissent that are not in any manner merely immaterial, given the ontic and de-ontic agency of such works. The goal (ethos and telos, as force-field) for such works would be found through actualization (but not mere praxis, which is instrumentality proper), and through charting an escape route for artist-scholars as outriders. The escape route would only appear through the focus on works-based agency; and the telos, as such, would not purport an end in itself but an end to unnecessary mediation. In the past this has been denoted immemoriality, and, whether of the post-phenomenological variety or the more archaic variety, immemoriality is – for artist-scholars – a reserve function in art and scholarship that relies on the cognates of a time-sense that is very close to sublimation – but dialectical sublimation versus continuous sublimation.³⁷

A central concern is “when” critique becomes commodified, plus “how” it becomes commodified. A central tenet of the post-contemporary, immanentist paradox inhabited by artist-scholars is that critique proper (whether cultural and/or political) has been serially ravaged by both careerism and authorial privileges – i.e., a forced slow march through institutions (e.g., in the case of art and scholarship, via the art-academic industrial complex), plus the false necessity of engaging with the protocols and biases of institutions and patriarchal culture.

The knowledge or creative commons (terms developed by late-modern capitalism and its various service industries, inclusive of the art world and academia) thus becomes suspect terrain for developing new forms of radical-democratic artistic and/or scholarly insurrection. The default position, also quite possibly pre-determined by Capital and its allies, is, then, the proverbial “back foot” (scare quotes required) – a position for dissidents that also has become mired in the attendant discourse of biopolitics. Colonization of heart and mind proceeds through occlusion of parallel realities and parallel time-senses in/for works. Thus, one possible (or suitably “impossible”) means to no ends is to explore and elaborate parallel realities and parallel time-senses for works, versus for any specific socio-cultural or socio-political gain. Mediation and patronage of a classical order may suggest that anything thus produced is by default a “product.” Yet the actual point of purchase for the establishment of a new ecosystem for works of artistic scholarship with no relation to Capital is the negation of commodity status.

In this manner “works for works” (as category experience) becomes – via privileging works-based agency versus authorial presence – a proleptic subjective state by which the subjective state of the author is duly liberated from the ravages of the forced slow march. The peculiar and ironic, the aleatory and the generative, and the absurd and the ridiculous quite often counter and/or expose the occlusions inculcated in works by censorial power. The escape route that appears is also highly temporal and must be guarded. To guard it, any editioning of new such works must also undermine and subvert the prevailing ecosystem for works as maintained and policed by Capital and its service industries, defining “on the run” an emergent ecosystem that restores what has been destroyed or repressed by the colonization processes of vectorial capitalist agendas. Ultimately what is at stake is the “free” human subject. The remaining question is, “Can this monkish sensorium (both severe and absurd) also become a *scriptorium* for new works-based agency, versus mere works, that has no relation whatsoever to Capital and its intended conquest of human subjectivity?”

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[...]

³⁷ For example, in *The Psychoanalysis of Fire*, Gaston Bachelard claims that dialectical sublimation is the form observed by Novalis across his life-work ... Gaston Bachelard, *The Psychoanalysis of Fire*, trans. Alan C.M. Ross (Boston: Beacon Press, 1964). First published *La psychanalyse du feu* (Paris: Vrin, 1938).